

MATERIAL VERSUS BUSINESS MODEL SELECTION: WHAT INFLUENCES THE ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT OF PACKAGING MORE?

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Abstract: *The environmental impacts of packaging have been discussed in scientific literature (e.g. Civancik-Uslu et al. 2019) and among political authorities (e.g. European Commission (EC)) alike. Concerns regarding environmental impacts of packaging and overall efficiency in material use have led to numerous regulations and strategies, for instance the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (European Union 1994), as well as the Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (EC 2018). However, in most cases, the function of packaging (e.g. product protection) can be fulfilled using alternative solutions, like using different materials (e.g. glass or plastics) or other business models (e.g. refund, refill systems), which would also support the circularity of products in use (Lofthouse et al. 2017). To date, there have not been many empirical studies approaching a comparison of the environmental impacts associated with these distinct solutions. This study presents a comparative LCA of various packaging materials (glass, PE, PLA) as well as different business model solutions (single-use, refill system) for a standard packaging of a cosmetic product. A streamlined LCA analysis from cradle to grave has been performed. The environmental impacts of a refill system were compared with the impacts of the single-use packaging solution. Due to the low level of technological maturity of the refill station, the environmental break-even point was calculated in comparison with a single-use packaging for a cosmetic product. The results show that switching the material to a more sustainable alternative can provide several environmental benefits. However, alternative business models have a stronger influence on the environmental impacts than*

material selection. This does not necessarily imply that they always provide environmental advances, but that factors such as user frequency, customer loyalty and behavior are decisive. Accordingly, we propose to integrate these factors into the environmental assessment of packaging solutions in the future.

Keywords: life cycle assessment, refill station, cosmetics packaging, circular economy, environmental break-even point

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